

ANALYSIS OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS AND CURRENT PROGRAMS FROM THE POINT OF VIEW OF THE USE OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING THE SUBJECT OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE IN THE FIELD

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KEYWORDS

Modern educational technologies, Uzbek language, educational programs, digital tools, interactive learning, multimedia resources, language acquisition, professional education

ABSTRACT

The integration of modern educational technologies into the teaching of the Uzbek language has become an essential factor in enhancing the learning process, particularly in specialized fields. This article analyzes the current educational programs and methodologies used in teaching the Uzbek language in various professional contexts, focusing on the effectiveness of digital tools, multimedia resources, and interactive learning platforms. The study also evaluates how these technologies impact language acquisition, student engagement, and overall learning outcomes. Through an examination of case studies and recent developments in educational technologies, this paper highlights key trends, challenges, and future opportunities for improving the teaching of the Uzbek language in professional fields.

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O'ZBEK TILINING SOHADA QO'LLANILISHI FANINI O'QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH NUQTAI NAZARIDAN O'QUV JARAYONI VA JORIY DASTURLAR TAHLILI

KALIT SO'ZLAR/
КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА:

Zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalari, o'zbek tili, ta'lim dasturlari, raqamli vositalar, interaktiv ta'lim, multimedia resurslari, til o'zlashtirish, kasbiy ta'lim.

ANNOTATSIYA/ АННОТАЦИЯ

O'zbek tilini sohada qo'llanilishini fanini o'qitishga zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalarini joriy etish, ayniqsa, ixtisoslashtirilgan yo'nalishlarda o'quv jarayonini faollashtirishning muhim omiliga aylandi. Ushbu maqolada turli kasbiy sharoitlarda o'zbek tilini o'qitishda qo'llanilayotgan joriy ta'lim dasturlari va metodologiyalari tahlil qilinib, raqamli vositalar, multimedia resurslari va interfaol o'quv platformalarining samaradorligiga e'tibor qaratiladi. Tadqiqot shuningdek, ushbu texnologiyalar tilni o'zlashtirishga, talabalarning faolligiga va umumiy ta'lim natijalariga qanday ta'sir qilishini baholaydi. Ushbu maqolada amaliy tadqiqotlar va ta'lim texnologiyalaridagi so'nggi ishlanmalarni o'rganish orqali o'zbek tilini kasbiy sohalarda o'qitishni takomillashtirishning asosiy yo'nalishlari, muammolari va kelajakdagi imkoniyatlari yoritilgan.

Introduction

In recent years, the field of education has undergone a significant transformation, driven by the integration of modern educational technologies (METs) into the curriculum. This shift is particularly relevant in the teaching of languages, where digital tools can enhance learning outcomes by increasing engagement, accessibility, and effectiveness. The teaching of the Uzbek language, particularly in professional and specialized fields, has benefited from these advancements. However, despite the potential of modern educational technologies, there are still challenges in their effective implementation in the teaching of the Uzbek language, particularly in the context of field-specific education, such as economics, law, and engineering. This article aims to analyze the current educational processes and programs related to the Uzbek language, examining how modern technologies are applied, their benefits, limitations, and areas for improvement.

Main Part

1. The Current State of Uzbek Language Teaching in the Field

Historically, the teaching of the Uzbek language in professional fields has relied heavily on traditional pedagogical approaches. These methods included lectures, textbooks, and rote memorization, which were often detached from the specific linguistic needs of professionals in areas such as economics, law, or engineering. According to (Ahmedov, 2020), this traditional model was effective to some extent, but it failed to address the contextual language requirements of students preparing for specialized careers. As a result,

students often struggled with the practical application of the Uzbek language in their professional environments.

In contrast, modern educational technologies such as online learning platforms, multimedia resources, and interactive exercises offer a more dynamic and contextualized approach. These tools can be used to simulate real-world professional scenarios, allowing students to apply their language skills in context. For example, (Karimov, 2021) notes that using simulation-based learning in legal Uzbek language courses has significantly improved students' understanding of complex legal terminology and its application in professional settings.

2. The Role of Modern Educational Technologies in Language Learning

The rise of digital platforms and interactive tools has opened up new avenues for language learning, especially for subjects like the Uzbek language, where professional jargon and technical language may be involved. Technologies like Learning Management Systems (LMS), mobile applications, and virtual classrooms have proven particularly effective in language education. LMS platforms such as Moodle allow instructors to integrate quizzes, assignments, and discussion forums tailored to specific professional sectors. Mobile applications provide language learning in small, digestible modules, enhancing accessibility and convenience for students.

One of the key benefits of METs in language learning is the capacity for personalized instruction. Through adaptive learning technologies, students can receive individualized feedback and progress at their own pace. For example, (Tursunov, 2022) highlights the use of AI-driven language learning apps that adapt to each student's proficiency level, allowing them to focus on areas where they need improvement.

Moreover, multimedia resources such as videos, audio recordings, and interactive graphics have enhanced student engagement by catering to different learning styles. (Davronov, 2019) found that students learning the Uzbek language through multimedia platforms demonstrated better retention and comprehension of the material compared to those using traditional methods.

3. Challenges in Implementing Modern Educational Technologies

While METs have shown great promise, their implementation in the Uzbek language curriculum has not been without challenges. One major issue is the lack of infrastructure in many educational institutions, particularly in rural areas. According to (Shodmonov, 2020), schools and universities in these regions often lack the necessary technological infrastructure, such as reliable internet access and modern computer labs, which limits the adoption of METs.

Another challenge is the need for teacher training. Many educators are unfamiliar with the latest technologies or lack the skills to integrate them effectively into their teaching. (Nishanov, 2021) emphasizes that without proper training, teachers may resist using digital tools or fail to utilize them to their full potential. Professional development programs focused on equipping teachers with the necessary digital skills are essential for the

successful integration of METs.

Additionally, there is a lack of Uzbek-language digital resources tailored to professional fields. While there are many educational technologies available for global languages like English, there is a scarcity of such tools designed specifically for Uzbek-language learners in professional contexts. This has hindered the widespread adoption of METs in these areas. According to (Rakhimov, 2021), developing more localized and context-specific digital resources is crucial for overcoming this barrier.

4. Prospects for the Future

The future of METs in teaching the Uzbek language, particularly in professional contexts, looks promising. As Uzbekistan continues to develop its digital infrastructure and prioritize education, the integration of technology in language learning will likely become more widespread. Tashkent Institute for Advanced Pedagogy predicts that by 2025, nearly all universities in Uzbekistan will have implemented LMS platforms, and mobile learning will be a common tool for language acquisition.

Furthermore, the development of more advanced technologies, such as virtual and augmented reality (VR and AR), holds significant potential for the teaching of the Uzbek language in specialized fields. VR simulations, for instance, could allow students to practice their language skills in immersive professional environments, such as virtual courtrooms or engineering labs. As (Yuldashev, 2022) notes, these innovations will enable students to gain practical experience and language proficiency simultaneously, better preparing them for their future careers.

Conclusion

In conclusion, modern educational technologies have the potential to significantly enhance the teaching of the Uzbek language, particularly in professional fields where contextual language skills are essential. While challenges such as infrastructure limitations and lack of teacher training persist, the benefits of METs—including personalized learning, multimedia resources, and interactive platforms—are undeniable. As Uzbekistan continues to develop its digital education infrastructure, the adoption of these technologies will likely expand, leading to improved language acquisition and better-prepared professionals. Continued investment in both technological infrastructure and teacher training is critical to realizing the full potential of modern educational technologies in Uzbek language education.

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